

Determining magnesium and silicon abundances from CARMENES spectra

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Abstract. The study of chemical abundances of stars that host planets is critical to our current understanding of the structure, formation, evolution of rocky planets, and to understand the evolution and assembly of the Milky Way. Here we present the abundances of magnesium (Mg) and silicon (Si) for 314 dwarf stars with spectral types in the range K7.0-M5.5 observed using the high-resolution CARMENES spectrograph. Our spectroscopic analysis employs the BT-Settl model atmospheres, the radiative transfer code Turbospectrum, and a state-of-the-art selection of atomic and molecular data. The derived chemical abundances have a line-to-line scatter at the level of 0.1 dex for all studied spectral types, which is unprecedented at the latest sub-types. Based on the comparison of the results obtained for stellar components of multiple systems, we find that the total error bar for these abundances is at the level of 0.2 dex. Our computed abundances are broadly consistent with the galactic evolution trends of earlier FGK-type stars in the solar neighbourhood. Finally, we also explore the relation of the Mg and Si abundances of stars with and without known exoplanets.

Observations, data reduction, and spectroscopic analysis:

Our sample contains 314 nearby K and M dwarfs observed within the framework of the CARMENES guaranteed time observations (GTO, see Reiners et al. 2018; Ribas et al. 2023) and legacy programs. Their spectra were reduced according to the standard CARMENES GTO data flow with the caracal and serval pipelines (Caballero et al. 2016; Zechmeister et al. 2018). Further details on the telluric correction and how these template spectra were computed can be found in Nagel et al. (2023). We used the spectral synthesis method to compute the abundances of Mg and Si of our target K and M stars. Our analysis employed six Mg I lines and six Si I lines. The spectral synthesis was done using the radiative transfer code Turbospectrum (Plez 2012). We employed the BT-Settl model atmospheres (Allard et al. 2012) covering the range from 2600 to 4500 K in Teff with a step of 100 K, 4.0 to 6.0 dex in log(g) with a step of 0.5 dex, and the following metallicity ([Fe/H]) values: -1.0, -0.5, +0.0, +0.3, and +0.5 dex. Finally, we assumed the stellar parameters computed by Marfil et al. (2021) using the STEPARSYN code (Tabernero et al. 2022).

Fig. 1: [X/Fe] vs. [Fe/H] for both Mg (left panel) and Si (right panel). Our target stars are represented by orange circles while the black open circles represent the abundances derived by for 1111 FGK stars from Adibekyan et al. (2012).

Fig. 2: Comparison in both [Mg/H] (left panel) and [Si/H] (right panel) between the components in multiple systems. The systems that contain an FGK+M pair are in blue while the M+M systems are in orange. The abundances of the FGK stars were taken from Montes et al. (2018).

References. Adibekyan et al. 2012, A&A, 545, A32; Allard et al. 2012, Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London Series A, 370, 2765; Caballero et al. 2016, SPIE, Vol. 9910, 99100E; Marfil et al. 2021, A&A, 656, A162; Montes et al. 2018, MNRAS, 479, 1332; Nagel et al. 2023, A&A, 680, A63; Plez 2012, Turbospectrum: code for spectral synthesis, ASCL; Reiners et al. 2018, A&A, 612, A49; Ribas et al. 2023, 670, A139; Santos et al. 2017, A&A, 608, A94; Tabernero et al. 2022, A&A, 657, A66; Tabernero et al. 2024, A&A, 689, A223; Zechmeister et al. 2018, A&A, 609, A12

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Fig. 3: Normalised cumulative histograms for [Fe/H], [Mg/Fe], and [Si/Fe] for the stars analysed in this work. The stars have been separated into two populations: stars with known planets (red) and stars without known planets (green). Our statistical analysis reveals that the two distributions are not significantly different according to a Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test.

Fig. 4: **Left:** [Si/Fe] vs. f_{iron} . The target stars are in orange while the black points correspond to the f_{iron} values computed from the Adibekyan et al. (2012) abundances. The fit through the M dwarf values is denoted with a blue line. **Right:** Histogram for the f_{iron} values of our sample.

Summary:

- We computed the magnesium and silicon abundances of 314 K- and M-type dwarfs observed by the CARMENES survey(s) (down to M5.5 V).
- We compared our results for galactic trends of [Mg/Fe] and [Si/Fe] vs. [Fe/H] with the values derived by Adibekyan et al. (2012) and found that both trends are compatible within error bars (Fig. 1).
- We compared the abundances of Mg and Si derived by Montes et al. (2018) to six M companions to FGK stars in the CARMENES sample. From this comparison, we found that our Mg and Si abundances are consistent at the 0.1–0.2 dex (Fig. 2).
- We compared the abundances of stars with and without planets and found that no clear statistical connection exists between the abundances and the incidence of planets (Fig. 3).
- We computed the iron fraction (f_{iron} , see Fig. 4) values as in Santos et al. (2017) and found that the M dwarfs should produce (on average) similar rocky planets to that of the FGK stars.